

A MICROMECHANICAL APPROACH TO VISCOELASTICITY OF UNIDIRECTIONAL HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Combination of the well-known rule of mixture and the classical theory of linear viscoelasticity leads to a stress-strain relation that effectively predicts the viscoelastic behavior of hybrid composites in uniaxial extension. The stress-strain relation is experimentally verified under isothermal conditions for an unidirectional hybrid system HP-PE/aramid/epoxy composite in dynamic forced vibration experiments. The micromechanical model leads to numerical predictions which are in good agreement with experimental data on composites with various compositions.

KEYWORDS: Hybrid; Fiber, Polyethylene; Fiber, Aramid; Matrix, Epoxy; Testing/Characterisation; Viscoelastic; Modelling.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is generally accepted that the longitudinal tensile modulus of hybrid composites obeys the rule of mixture (ROM) [1]. As demonstrated by Hashin, for a composite based on a viscoelastic matrix and elastic fibers, the ROM can be easily incorporated in the classical theory of linear viscoelasticity [2].

In this study, the same basic modelling is applied to unidirectional composites based

on viscoelastic fibers, in an attempt to derive a mathematical relation that can be used to evaluate the viscoelastic behavior of these materials on the basis of the properties of their components. The relation is experimentally verified using the HP-PE/aramid/epoxy system, where all components display significant viscoelastic behavior.

For simplicity the study is performed for isothermal loading conditions (30 °C) while the viscoelastic characterisation is restricted to relatively short loading times ($0.01 \text{ s} < t < 10000 \text{ s}$). Moreover, the components are regarded to be linearly viscoelastic in a first approximation.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials The fibers used in this study were a HP-PE fiber (Dyneema SK60, 400 den) supplied by DSM high performance fibers BV, and an aramid fiber (Twaron-HM, 1500 den) supplied by AKZO. A common epoxy system, CIBA Geigy's Araldite LY556/HY917/DY070, based on Bisphenol A with an anhydride curing agent, was used as the principal matrix.

Unidirectional (UD) composites were prepared by a modified pultrusion process. Bundles containing aramid and/or HP-PE yarns were immersed in a bath of epoxy resin and pulled into moulds with PTFE inserts squeezing out the surplus on resin and trapped air. The samples were cured for 4 h at 80 °C and postcured at 110 °C for 12 h. Using this pultrusion technique, circular specimens with a diameter of 1.2 mm were prepared. The volume fraction of HP-PE and/or aramid fibers was varied, whereas the total volume fraction of fibers was 30 to 40%. The composites obtained by this procedure are denoted by the HP-PE volume fraction versus the aramid volume fraction; 0.163/0.195, for instance, is a composite consisting of 16.3 % HP-PE fiber and 19.5 % aramid fiber.

For characterisation of the pure epoxy matrix, epoxy films of about 0.1 mm thickness were prepared by curing in a hot press for 4 h at 80 °C at a pressure of 5 bar and postcuring for 12 h at 110 °C.

2.2 Mechanical testing All mechanical experiments were performed at a constant temperature of 30 °C. Stress-relaxation experiments, with loading times not exceeding 3 hrs [3,4], were performed on a Frank 81565 tensile tester equipped with a thermostatically controlled oven and an extensometer. Unless stated otherwise, fiber samples with a length of 255 mm were used. To avoid slippage in the clamps, the fiber samples were provided with adhesively bonded cardboard tabs.

The UD-composite specimens had an overall length of 300 mm. To improve clamping, the ends of the specimens were provided with glass tubes (diameter 6 mm, bore 1.5 mm, length 50 mm), which were adhesively bonded to the specimen. The specimens were clamped by enclosing the glass tubes in specially shaped grips, that applied the load directly to the glass tubes.

All samples, except the epoxy films, were previously conditioned by loading at a constant strain level of 1% for a period of 1 minute.

The dynamic properties of the HP-PE fiber in uniaxial extension were studied using Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA MK2, Polymer Laboratories) at frequencies of 0.2 to 3 Hz and temperatures between 0 and 90 °C [3,4]. The samples were 20 mm long and had a cross-sectional area of about 0.01 mm². To avoid buckling of the fiber as a result of the dynamic strain amplitude (0.05 %), a static load of 150 MPa was applied.

Dynamic experiments on aramid fiber, epoxy and the composite materials were performed on a Zwick Rel servo-hydraulic tensile tester (20 kN) that was adapted for application of white noise strain excitation [4]. In the experiment a dynamic strain (amplitude 0.1%) was superimposed on a statically applied strain of 0.5%. The dynamic strain excitation consisted of 256 frequencies in the range of 0 to 10 Hz, where all frequencies contributed with equal amplitude (so-called "white" noise). Stress output and strain input were transformed into dynamic quantities using a HP 98785A Fast Fourier Analyser in the frequency range from 0.1 to 5 Hz.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Modelling For a linear viscoelastic material, the Boltzmann superposition principle applied to uniaxial extension leads to [5]:

$$\sigma(t) = \int_0^t E(t-t') \dot{\epsilon}(t') dt \quad (1)$$

This convolution integral provides a mathematical equation that relates viscoelastic stress to strain under various loading conditions. The time-dependent behavior is characterised by a viscoelastic function, in this case the stress relaxation modulus $E(t)$. For prediction of the mechanical behavior of a viscoelastic material using Eq. (1), a mathematical description of this viscoelastic function is needed that covers a sufficiently wide time/frequency range.

In the case of continuous fiber reinforcement, the deformation behavior of unidirectional composites in uniaxial extension can be considered the result of matrix

and fibers acting in parallel. This leads to the well-known ROM which relates the Young's modulus of a composite to the Young's moduli its components.

In conformity with the ROM, it can easily be deduced that the stress relaxation modulus of the composite is related to the stress relaxation moduli of its components in the following manner:

$$E_{comp}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n v_i E_i(t) \quad (2)$$

where $E_{comp}(t)$ represents the stress relaxation modulus of the composite, and E_i represents the stress relaxation modulus of the i -th component. The volume fraction of the i -th component is represented by v_i .

Once the viscoelastic functions $E_i(t)$ are known, the introduction of Eq. (2) into Eq. (1) leads to a mathematical expression that is able to predict the viscoelastic behavior of a composite material in various compositions.

Laplace transform of the stress-strain relation leads to the following expressions for the dynamic modulus E_d and the loss angle δ as a function of frequency [4]:

$$E_{d,comp}(\omega) = \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^n v_i E_i'(\omega) \right)^2 + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n v_i E_i''(\omega) \right)^2 \right]^{0.5} \quad (3)$$

$$\delta_{comp}(\omega) = \arctan \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n v_i E_i''(\omega)}{\sum_{i=1}^n v_i E_i'(\omega)} \right) \quad (4)$$

where the storage modulus E' and the loss modulus E'' represent the real and imaginary part of the complex modulus.

3.2 Component characterisation In the case of HP-PE fibers, it has been shown [3] that a mathematical description for the stress relaxation modulus can be successfully obtained by introduction of a relaxation spectrum [5]:

$$E(t) = E_{\infty} + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H(\tau) \exp\left(\frac{-t}{\tau}\right) d(\ln\tau) \quad (5)$$

where $H(\tau)$ is the continuous relaxation spectrum. In practice the lower and upper boundaries of the integral are limited to the finite values $\ln\tau_{\min}$ and $\ln\tau_{\max}$. The introduction of an elastic part of the stress relaxation modulus E_{∞} is convenient from

a mathematical point of view, as it reduces the width ($\ln\tau_{\max} - \ln\tau_{\min}$) of the spectrum needed for accurate description of the experimental data.

Similar expressions as Eq. (5) are known to relate the dynamic quantities E' and E'' to the relaxation spectrum [5].

In order to derive the relaxation spectrum, the dynamic properties of the HP-PE fiber were experimentally evaluated by means of isothermal frequency scans in the range from 0 to 90 °C [4]. Master curves of E_d and $\tan \delta$, constructed by horizontal shifting and matching of adjacent curves, are presented in Fig. 1 for a reference temperature of 30 °C. As time-temperature superposition is allowed for HP-PE fibers, master curves obtained in this way can be used quite effectively to predict the actual fiber behavior up to loading times of 10^6 s [3].

From these master curves the continuous relaxation spectrum can be derived easily, employing the method described in [4]. The continuous relaxation spectrum $H(\tau)$ derived from the master curves in Fig. 1 is represented in Fig. 2. An additional equilibrium modulus of 25.65 GPa was needed to allow proper description of the dynamic modulus and $\tan \delta$ (Fig. 1) over the frequency range experimentally covered.

In the case of aramid fiber and epoxy, the characterisation procedure is relatively straight forward. Stress relaxation experiments indicate that both materials display a power law relaxation behavior with time [4], where:

$$E(t) = C t^{-n} \quad (6)$$

This approximation of the stress relaxation behavior leads to comprehensive analytical expressions for the dynamic modulus E_d and the loss angle δ as a function of the angular frequency ω [5]:

$$E_d(\omega) = C \Gamma(1-n) \omega^n \quad (7)$$

$$\delta(\omega) = \frac{n\pi}{2} \quad (8)$$

where $\omega = 2\pi f$ and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma-function.

In Fig. 3 the experimental values of the dynamic modulus (Fig. 3a) and $\tan \delta$ (Fig. 3b) are compared with power law predictions (Eqs. (7) and (8)). It is clear that the power law approximation holds over a large frequency region for both aramid fiber and epoxy. The power law coefficients used to predict the dynamic quantities were derived from stress relaxation data [4], and are listed in table 1.

Figure 1. Master curves of the dynamic modulus (\diamond) and $\tan \delta$ (\circ) of HP-PE vs the logarithm of the angular frequency for a reference temperature of 30 °C. The solid lines represent the numerical predictions from the continuous relaxation spectrum of Fig. 2.

Figure 2. The continuous relaxation spectrum $H(\tau)$ of HP-PE fibre at a reference temperature of 30 °C.

Figure 3. (a) Dynamic moduli and (b) $\tan \delta$ of aramid fiber and epoxy vs angular frequency measured at 30 °C, using "white" noise forced vibration experiments (solid lines). The symbols represent data from stress relaxation experiments [4], transformed to dynamic quantities using the power law approximation (dashed lines).

Figure 4. Numerical predictions (dashed lines) of (a) the dynamic moduli and (b) $\tan \delta$ of various composites compared with data of "white" noise forced vibration experiments at 30 °C. The composites are denoted (HP-PE fraction)/(aramid fraction)

TABLE 1. Power law coefficients for aramid fiber and epoxy, as derived from stress relaxation data [4].

Material	C [GPas ⁿ]	n [-]
Aramid fiber	119.4	0.010
Epoxy	2.9	0.025

3.3 Model verification The validity of this simple micromechanical approach was evaluated in dynamic ("white" noise) experiments. Numerical predictions of the dynamic quantities E_d and $\tan \delta$ of the composite were obtained using Eqs. (3) and (4). For aramid fiber and epoxy E' and E'' were calculated from the power law predictions of E_d and $\tan \delta$ (Eqs. (7) and (8)), using the coefficients given in Table 1. For HP-PE the storage and loss moduli, E' and E'' , were calculated as a function of frequency from the continuous relaxation spectrum in Fig.2 [3,4]. The results are presented in Fig. 4a and 4b, where a good agreement between the model predictions and the experimental data can be observed.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Combination of the ROM and the classical theory of linear viscoelasticity leads to a stress-strain relation that effectively predicts the mechanical behavior of hybrid composites in uniaxial extension under various loading conditions. Although the stress-strain relation was only verified in a rather limited frequency range, it is inherently able, even on the basis of the component characterisation performed in this study, to describe the composite behavior over a much larger frequency range.

As the ROM can be applied directly to determine the longitudinal tensile-, storage- and loss-moduli of composite materials, the use of the stress-strain relation, presented in this study, might seem a cumbersome procedure. However, it supplies a comprehensive mathematical basis for a fast numerical evaluation of the vibrational damping properties of UD-composites in various compositions.

5. REFERENCES

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